

Public Perception of Biodiversity Landscape Elements and Autonomous Technologies in Small-Scale Production Systems

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Background | Small-Scale Production Systems

- Strip Intercropping approach (Vandermeer, 1989)
 - Small-scale, mixed cropping system, crop rotation, biodiversity, soil erosion control
 - Can autonomous technologies make working in small systems more economical? (Lowenberg-DeBoer, 2021)
- ‘Aesthetic appearance’ of landscape and perception of agricultural practices by non-agricultural population
- Experience and functional knowledge influencing the visual assessment (Dentzmann and Goldberger, 2020)
 - Farmers’ evaluation of landscape differs from non-agricultural society (Burton, 2012)

Future Crop Farming – biodiverse – soil-friendly – digital

Objectives | Expectations and Study Goals

Farmers vs. non-agricultural population

- Conservation measures & structural elements can be associated with 'disorder' or 'naturalness'; linearity as 'functional' or 'unnatural' (Laroche et al, 2018)
- Autonomous technologies equated with alienation of agriculture? (Spykman et al., 2021, Willmes et al., 2022)
- Relevance of a positive visual evaluation by society for the acceptance of landscape changes (Warren Kretschmar and von Haaren, 2014)

Study goals:

- Analysis of German population's perception of small-scale diversified cropping systems with structural elements and autonomous technologies
- Identification of triggers for rejection or endorsement (spontaneous associations)
- Segmentation analysis to identify sociodemographic influences on preferences

Material & Methods | Data Collection and Methodology

Material & Methods | Choice of Image Variants

**Robot/
without
flower strip**

**Tractor/
without
flower strip**

**Robot/
with flower
strip**

**Tractor/
with flower
strip**

Material & Methods | Data Collection

1. Variant selection

Images differing in two features (robot/tractor & with/without flowers trips) all shown next to each other

2. Ranking of most decisive image components (3/6)

- Robot in the field
- 1 Tractor on the field
- Flower strip between the fields
- 3 Tidiness of the adjacent field strips
- Beautiful row of trees
- 2 Other reasons

Weighted order of the three selected image components

3. Association of short keywords (component #1)

Keyword 1	<i>Tradition</i>
Keyword 2	<i>Field work</i>
Keyword 3	<i>familiar</i>

Total of 4,872 usable keywords

Material & Methods | Measuring Demographics & Attitudes

- Sociodemographics
Gender, Age, Education, Size of place of residence, region (East/West)
- Own experience in agriculture or food sector (yes/no)
- Personal contact with farmers (yes/no)
- Attitude (5-point Likert-type scales)
 - Green consumption value (GCV)
 - Attitude towards technology (ATT)→ Standardised factor scores

- Logistic regression models to capture the probabilities of preferences for Flower strips & Robots

Distribution of the factor values for green consumption value (GCV) and the attitude towards technology (ATT) of the respondents (n = 2,022); GVC: median: -0.11; skewness: 0.774; kurtosis: 0.525; ATT: median: -0.09, skewness: 0.339; kurtosis: -0.127

Scales adapted from Haws et al (2014), Edison & Geissler (2003)

Results | 1. Preferences and Selection Motives

Variant selection

Without flower strips

With flower strips

Distribution of distinct image components (rank-weighted)

Robot

Tractor

Results | 2. Factors influencing Preferences

Predictors Model 'Robot'	B	SE	Wald	p	Odds Ratio	95% CI	
						LL	UL
Gender (1=female)*	-0.835	0.337	6.137	0.013	0.434	0.224	0.840
Age (1=younger than 40 years)	0.067	0.392	0.029	0.864	1.069	0.496	2.304
Education (1=no A-levels)	0.100	0.332	0.090	0.764	1.105	0.576	2.118
Size of place of residence (1=less than 20k inhabitants)	-0.288	0.342	0.706	0.401	0.750	0.384	1.467
Region (1=Western Germany states)	-0.314	0.367	0.730	0.393	0.731	0.356	1.501
Own agricultural experience (1=yes)	0.405	0.670	0.365	0.545	1.499	0.403	5.572
Personal contact with farmers (1=yes)*	-2.088	1.043	4.008	0.045	0.124	0.016	0.957
Attitude towards technology (ATT) (negative factor value = higher degree)	-0.034	0.141	0.059	0.808	0.966	0.732	1.275
Green Consumption Value (GCV) (negative factor value = higher degree)	0.087	0.178	0.239	0.625	1.091	0.770	1.546
Constant***	-1.398	0.406	11.892	0.000	0.247		

Note: ***p<0.001, *p<0.05; $\chi^2(9) = 16.460$, p = 0.058; Nagelkerke's R² = 0.076; (Cox & Snell R² = 0.036) | Total percentage of assignment classification (contribution of predictor variables) = 90.3% | Source: own survey

Results | 2. Factors influencing Preferences

Predictors Model 'Flower strip'	B	SE	Wald	p	Odds Ratio	95% CI	
						LL	UL
Gender (1=female)	0.272	0.244	1.250	0.264	1.313	0.814	2.117
Age (1=younger than 40 years)***	-0.966	0.262	13.602	0.000	0.381	0.228	0.636
Education (1= no A-levels) ^a	-0.228	0.244	0.876	0.069	0.796	0.493	1.284
Size of place of residence (1=less than 20k inhabitants)*	0.451	0.248	3.305	0.049	1.570	0.965	2.554
Region (1=Western Germany states) ^a	0.519	0.267	3.791	0.052	1.681	0.997	2.835
Own agricultural experience (1=yes)	-0.470	0.431	1.189	0.276	0.625	0.268	1.455
Personal contact with farmers (1=yes)	0.260	0.368	0.499	0.480	1.297	0.630	2.669
Attitude towards technology (ATT) (negative factor value = higher degree)	0.033	0.104	0.101	0.751	1.034	0.843	1.268
Green Consumption Value (GCV) (negative factor value = higher degree)***	-0.428	0.141	9.146	0.002	0.652	0.494	0.860
Constant**	0.827	0.312	7.044	0.008	2.287		

Note: ***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05, a p<0.1; $\chi^2(9) = 37.843$, Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.122$; (Cox & Snell $R^2 = 0.080$) | total percentage of assignment classification (contribution of predictor variables) = 78.7% | source: own survey

Results | 3. Associations with Image Components

Keyword categories (examples)	Exemplary Keywords – associations (n=4,872; 33 categories)
Efficiency/Quality	<i>perfect work, robust, efficient, productive, fast, success, yield, optimisation</i>
Modern/Trendy/Progress	<i>modern, future, innovation, trend</i>
Facilitation of work	<i>labour saving, fast work, makes work easier</i>
Maintaining jobs	<i>workplace, human, craft, manual labour, professional maintenance, job</i>
Nostalgia	<i>former, past, childhood, memory</i>
Familiar image/Tradition	<i>familiar image, home, authentic, how it should be, normal, standard, typical, classic, traditional, down-to-earth</i>
Changes/Alternatives	<i>polyculture, no monoculture, loosening up, alternative</i>
Soil and soil protection	<i>(healthy) soil, nutrients, erosion control, soil protection, fertile</i>
Green/Nature/Environment	<i>nature, species diversity, biodiversity, bees, insect (protection), habitat, flora and fauna</i>
Neat & tidy	<i>conscientious, separate, clear line, weed-free, plan, care, clean, cleanliness, hygienic, uniform, clear, nature, species diversity, biodiversity, bees, insect (protection), habitat</i>
Well-being	<i>joy, friendly, fresh, life, good, happy, harmony, strength, active, calm, maturity, freedom, retreat, genuine</i>
Aesthetics	<i>beautiful, pretty, colourful, handsome, colourful, idyllic</i>

Results | 3. Evaluation of Keyword Associations

Counting for selected image 4 (2,995 keywords, most frequent categories)

	Flower strip (43%)		Tractor (28%)	
	Mentions	Rank	Mentions	Rank
Green/Nature/Environment	1,535	1	54	5
Aesthetics	347	2	21	8
Well-being	175	3	64	4
Changes, Alternatives	52	4	0	26
Soil and soil protection	43	5	5	14
Neat and tidy	37	6	9	10
Relevance/Useful	25	7	3	16
Agriculture in general	23	8	175	1
Season	21	9	2	20
Familiar image/Tradition	14	10	91	2
Nostalgia	11	11	31	6
Maintaining jobs	3	20	66	3
Efficiency/Quality	3	20	14	9
Work in general	2	22	25	7
Backward step/Old	0	30	3	16
Modern/Trendy/Progress	8	16	2	20
Total	2,299		565	

Conclusions | Result Summary

- Preferences for inclusion of flower strips and *familiar* components (tractor)
- Image variant with a robot and flower strip is chosen about as often as that with a tractor but without a flower strip
- Use of autonomous technologies for fieldwork is not fundamentally viewed critically (*innovation, 'neutral' associations*) (Pfeiffer et al. 2020)
- Relevance of orderly structure and the categories of *aesthetics* and *green/nature/environment* with or without flower strips

Conclusions | Discussion and Outlook

- Strip intercropping is not generally rejected; preferences for *natural*, 'near-natural' and *familiar* images
- Strong awareness of environmental issues, soil protection and changes/alternatives
- Robots are not widespread yet; degree of autonomy is considered as secondary to the reduction of herbicides in food production (Spykman et al., 2022)
- Future studies should consider additional factors such as the population's knowledge of farming practices or attitudes towards ecology and nature.
- Social perception and the broader ecological context must not be overlooked to also consider the societal perspective on changes in landscape structures.

Thank you for your interest!

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